

**ORAL AND SILENT READING PROFICIENCY AND ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH AMONG GRADE SEVEN
LEARNERS: ENHANCED READING
REMEDICATION PROGRAM**

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Oral and Silent Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance in English among Grade Seven Learners: Enhanced Reading Remediation Program

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Abstract

The study determined the relationship of oral and silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English among grade 7 learners in Tipolo National High School for School Year 2022-2023 as basis for an enhanced reading remediation program using descriptive correlation research design. The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) materials were used in assessing the level of reading proficiency among grade seven learners thru post test results and the 4th quarter or final ratings in English were used to assess the academic performance in English of the Grade 7 students at Tipolo National High School. The quantitative design of this study described the characteristics of the respondents including oral and silent reading proficiency level, and academic performance. The findings of the study revealed that Grade 7 Students are classified frustration in their oral and silent reading proficiency level. Based on the results obtained, it was concluded that oral reading had a positive weak correlation on the academic performance in English and this correlation was found to be statistically significant. In contrary, silent reading was not significantly related to the academic performance in English. The results supported the Information Processing Model Theory which promoted oral reading fluency strategies for learners and the Reading Systems Framework which highlighted various factors necessary in improving the complex reading process especially on word recognition and comprehension. Therefore, the results suggest that oral reading proficiency may have a more influential relationship with academic performance in English compared to silent reading proficiency. Consequently, the study would provide the English teachers with the enhanced reading remediation program in addition to the present intervention activities provided in the Phil-IRI package to address the reading difficulties among grade seven learners after the culmination of this research pursuit.

Keywords: *silent reading proficiency, oral reading proficiency, independent readers, instructional readers, frustration readers*

Introduction

Reading is the gateway to knowledge, the bridge that connects students to a world of information, ideas, and imagination. It's the bedrock of all learning, providing the foundation upon which academic success is built. The connection between reading proficiency and academic performance is profound and undeniable. When students possess strong reading skills, they not only excel in language and literacy subjects but also gain a crucial advantage in comprehending complex concepts across all disciplines. Proficient readers can absorb, analyze, and synthesize information effectively, empowering them to excel in exams, research, and critical thinking tasks. In essence, reading proficiency is the catalyst for academic achievement, a key that unlocks the doors to a brighter educational future. Moreover, Tipolo National High School, a notable urban institution known for its size and inclusive educational approach, faces a significant challenge related to students' reading difficulties. Many students are grappling with frustration as they struggle to pronounce words correctly and fully understand written materials, whether reading silently or aloud. This issue's complexity has become more apparent due to the disruptive impact of the pandemic. A key contributor to this problem is the lack of structured instruction and dedicated reading activities among students, exacerbated by the sudden shift to remote learning during the pandemic. The study underscores a research gap in the education field, particularly concerning learners' reading skills and their influence on academic performance. It highlights the absence of localized research that specifically explores the significance of oral and silent reading skills within the unique context of Tipolo National High School. Additionally, it emphasizes the challenge of developing precise and effective methods for improving reading remediation programs, calling for further research to provide evidence-based strategies tailored to the students' specific needs.

Tipolo National High School emerges as a focal point of concern within the educational landscape, notably highlighted by the findings of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for the academic year 2021-2022. Within the purview of the Mandaue City Division South District, a discernible pattern surfaces whereby Tipolo National High School stands distinctively as the sole institution grappling with a substantial cohort of learners performing below the frustration level threshold, as per the Phil-IRI assessment. A significant percentage of the student population there is struggling with frustration about their reading ability. The complex causes of this prevalent problem have become increasingly obvious as a result of the pandemic's destructive effects on society. One of the main causes is the absence of organized instruction and the apparent absence of dedicated reading activities within the student community. These concerns were made worse by the sudden switch to remote learning that the pandemic entailed. Students were consequently left without the structured reading practices that were previously provided in the context of the classroom and, as a result, had less access to reading materials and possibilities for independent practice.

According to the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) findings, the Philippines ranked last in reading based

on an examination of students' reading, math, and science knowledge conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. This emphasizes the pressing need to deal with deficiencies and inadequacies in order to improve the nation's basic education system. These core ability issues begin in the early stages, with a considerable proportion of pupils failing to demonstrate comprehension of what they are reading in English by the end of Grade 3. This insufficient skill in English severely limits children's learning abilities in all courses in later years.

Reading proficiency and academic performance are both essential to a learner's overall academic success and should not be neglected in any learning environment. Learners must be equipped with the skills to read and understand material accurately and quickly in order to be able to fully engage with the competency presented and reach their full potential.

Moreover, academic performance should be actively monitored and evaluated in order to ensure that learners are making steady progress in their studies. This is especially true for learners from different cultural backgrounds or with diverse linguistic needs, as their educational needs may be different from their peers. It is important for educators to recognize the relevance and significance of both reading proficiency and academic performance when it comes to providing a well-rounded education to all learners. With learners receiving the proper guidance and support, they can become independent and successful learners.

Reading is such a vital tool for academic success that teachers must ensure that all their learners are receiving the necessary instruction to help them become proficient readers. Koda and Zehler (2018) strongly emphasize the importance of reading in their research, noting that it is a cornerstone of academic learning and provides the reader with the knowledge needed to be successful in the world. Unfortunately, when a student struggles with reading, they are more likely to experience difficulty in all other subject areas as well. Without the ability to read at a certain level, learners are unable to fully access the resources that are needed to continue their learning. Therefore, it is of utmost importance that teachers provide additional support and resources to those who are struggling in both silent and oral reading. By doing so, they can help ensure that all learners have the opportunity to reach their full potential.

Without a doubt, understanding written and spoken languages as well as being able to express thoughts and concepts are essential to one's development and advancement. Understanding and communicating allow for access to knowledge in a variety of fields, and by mastering a variety of study techniques, routines, and attitudes, one can cultivate the passion required for lifelong learning. As a result, those who struggle with comprehension and communication are deprived of amazing opportunities to grow personally (Cimmiyotti, 2019).

In this situation, the primary element of need theory gave rise to the requirement of assessment. The assessment of learners' reading competency focuses mostly on an individual's internal organization and degree of mental organization. As a result, schools instruct kids on how to conduct themselves appropriately; nevertheless, there are a number of factors that influence how much is learnt and how much should be learned. In the end, the impact results in a number of learning discrepancies in the kids and poses significant issues for the entire educational system (Bryce, 2017).

Beginning to assess this complex situation, it becomes increasingly apparent that dealing with these difficulties is not just a social responsibility but also an educational necessity. Being able to recognize, identify, and address the complex issues that have impeded these students' reading development is crucial to realizing the future that lies hidden inside them. By undertaking this goal, this study seeks to show the way to a better educational future, helping not only the learners at Tipolo National High School but also the larger community. Effective reading interventions help students move from dissatisfaction to competency, raising a generation of literate people who are capable of excelling in their academic endeavors.

Learning is characterized as a process inferred from relatively persistent behavioral alterations brought about by repetition, interaction, and environmental adaptation. Thus, when interactions between various cognitive, psychomotor, and affective variables allow one to accomplish a given activity differently than one would normally, an individual may understand anything. Understanding and comprehension are crucial learning tools in this regard (Cromley, 2017).

The Department of Education has therefore started programs to deal with learners' reading issues. As DepEd Order No. 45 s. 2002, every kid should be able to read by the time they complete third grade, according to Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP), a national initiative. Teachers had run a number of intervention and remediation programs in response to the DepEd's request. However, studies revealed that the majority of learners who make it to Grades IV and higher still struggle with reading.

Moreover, Tipolo National High School, an urban, large, and integrated public high school has a great number of readers under frustration level. Most readers are having a hard time to pronounce and comprehend reading materials both in oral and silent approach. This has been identified to be due to many factors like lack of guidance and initiative of the learners in practicing reading at home during pandemic.

Hence, this study highlights a significant research gap within the field of education, particularly in the context of learners' reading proficiencies and their impact on academic performance. It underlines, first and foremost, the absence of extensive and locally performed research studies that explore the significance and relevance of both oral and silent reading skills with regard to how they affect students' academic performance. This discrepancy implies that although there is a general grasp of the importance of reading, particularly in terms of language development, there is a lack of concentrated study that specifically addresses this issue within the

context of Tipolo National High School.

Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the field in addressing the modern changes of 21st learners in their oral and silent reading proficiencies and providing a wide consideration as to its effect on the academic performance of the learners. This shall provide an intervention that is adoptive, foster a positive learning environment and student-friendly that will satisfy the gap of learners in the field of reading.

The majority of learners that excel at oral and non-oral communication in a classroom context are often achieving success in their academics. It should be understood, though, that communication skills are only one aspect of the learner's overall development.

Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the field in addressing the modern changes of 21st learners in their oral and silent reading proficiencies and providing a wide consideration as to its effect on the academic performance of the learners. This shall provide an intervention that is adoptive, foster a positive learning environment and student-friendly that will satisfy the gap of learners in the field of reading. The findings that will be derived from the study shall provide an expected output which is the enhancement of reading remediation program. This aims to significantly lower the number of learners who struggle tremendously with reading and writing. In both an individual and small group context, remedial reading is a very successful short-term solution for struggling readers. This shall help to identify struggling learners early on and shall provide them necessary support to be able to thrive in school. The goal is for the school to intervene, or step in, and start helping before a learner falls really far behind.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the relationship between the oral and silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English among grade 7 learners, School Year 2022-2023, as basis for a reading remediation program enhancement. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the oral reading proficiency level of Grade 7 learners?
2. What is the silent reading proficiency level of Grade 7 learners?
3. What is the academic performance of grade 7 learners in English?
4. Is there a significant relationship between silent and oral reading proficiency and learners' academic performance in English?
5. Based on the results of the study, what reading intervention program enhancement may be designed for the grade 7 learners of Tipolo National High School?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational design. This investigated the relationship between the oral and silent reading comprehension level of the grade 7 learners and their academic performance in English School Year 2022-2023. The quantitative design of this study described the characteristics of the respondents including reading comprehension level in both oral and silent reading and their academic performance in English. This study employed an adopted questionnaire: Phil-IRI from the Department of Education.

Further, this study was to determine whether there was a significant correlation between oral and silents reading proficiency to the learners' academic performance in English among grade 7 students for School Year 2022-2023.

Participants

The participants of the study were composed of 186 Grade 7 students of Tipolo National High School for the school year 2022-2023. All 4 sections in grade 7 were chosen to compose the population of this study. The respondents of the study were the sections handled by the researcher composed of 4 sections. There were 44 students in Grade 7- Amethyst, 48 students in Grade 7- Diamond, 51 students in Grade 8 - Ruby, and 47 students in Grade 7- Emerald, a total of 190 students officially enrolled. However, only 186 physically healthy students participated in the research study with the consent of their parents. The participants were asked to answer Phil-IRI, had their oral and silent reading proficiency level assessed, and compared them to their final rating in English 7 or their academic performance.

Therefore, the total number of respondents utilized for this research is 186, comprising 4 sections from grade seven. Furthermore, there was no selection of population to be used as a sample.

Instruments

This study utilized the Philippine – Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) materials in assessing the level of reading proficiency of the students in terms of oral and silent reading and the final rating of the students in English to see its correlation with their academic performance in English.

The Phil-IRI Reading tool is a multiple-choice test with 40 item questions. This comprises five selections with eight multiple-choice

questions for each. This was utilized to determine the oral and silent reading proficiency of the students.

The Phil-IRI is a widely recognized and validated assessment tool designed to evaluate both oral and silent reading skills among grade 7 learners. It provides a comprehensive framework for gauging learners' reading abilities, including word recognition, fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary knowledge. The utilization of the Phil-IRI in this research enabled a nuanced analysis of the learners' reading proficiency, shedding light on their ability to engage with written texts both orally and silently. The correlation between their reading proficiency and academic performance in English was explored, with the aim of enhancing the existing academic support programs and strategies for grade seven learners. The reading inventory tool has three levels: Independent, Instructional, Frustration. The lowest level is frustration, in which the learner refuses to read and withdraws from reading circumstances; instructional level, the learner profits or gains from education; independent, reader is self-sufficient and reads well without the instruction or assistance of a teacher/facilitator.

Procedure

This study was conducted during the school year 2022-2023 at Tipolo National High School. It considered the following technical procedure.

The research followed a well-structured process with distinct phases for accurate results. In the initial "Pre-Data Preliminaries" phase, the researcher made a title proposal and was approved by the Dean on the focus and direction of this study. Then, the researcher asked permission from the Dean of the Graduate School for the approval of the study. The researcher submitted a detailed proposal to the advisor and, upon approval, sent a key permission letter to Tipolo National High School. Subsequently, the researcher readied chapters one through three in preparation for the design hearing. Following this, was preparing, and ensuring ethical compliance as the revised manuscript was presented to the IRB for a thorough technical and ethical evaluation.

The "Actual Data Gathering" phase-maintained data confidentiality, validated responses through short interviews, and prepared data for comprehensive analysis. Finally, the "Post Data Procedure" involved analyzing data with various statistical methods to achieve study objectives, emphasized rigor, ethics, and valuable insights. Specifically, the following processes were conducted: The researcher underwent the following procedures to attain the essential data from its respondents:

Preliminary

In the preliminary step, the researcher submitted a proposal to the adviser for the approval of the title of the paper. The proposal contained all the details of the study. Once approved, a permission letter was submitted to the school head/ principal of Tipolo National High School to allow the conduct of the study on the participants that meet the requirement for the said study. The researcher obtained the tests from Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) Manual 2018 comprising questions addressing the need for a reading intervention program and academic performance of the students in reading proficiency to which the researcher set relative to the statement of the problem. The approved title was then submitted to the University of Visayas Institutional Review Board before proceeding to the data-gathering procedures.

Pre-data Collection

The data collection commenced upon approval of the research title by the Dean of the School of Education in the University of the Visayas. Afterwards, the researcher sent a formal letter to the principal and superintendent to seek permission to conduct a research study at Tipolo National High School grade 7 students. The researcher also sent a letter to the parents of the concerned grade 7 respondents asking permission to utilize their students as respondents of the research study. The content of the letter explained well the nature and purpose of conducting the study to the respondents. The parental consent was sent to the parents of all Grade 7 respondents. Another letter was also sent to the Institutional Review Board for the approval to conduct the research study to the learners as mandated by the privacy act of gathering information to the respondents. Moreover, prior to administering the adopted reading tool the researcher ensured that all consent was signed and verified the authenticity of respondent's parents' signatures, a briefing and orientation was conducted before administering the survey.

Actual

For the actual data-gathering, the data obtained from the participants were managed and kept confidential throughout the conduct of the study. The responses were stored in a file that is secured by a password, only accessible to the researcher. The validity of the responses was done by short interviews with the participants, students and parents. Then, the researcher prepared the data gathered for data processing; and lastly, was the carrying out of the comparative analysis from the yielded interpretation.

Data Collection Phase. The researcher conducted Oral and Silent reading examinations using the adopted Phi-IRI Reading tool during the respondent' English class time. It was done in their classroom with the consent of their adviser. Before the students answered the reading examination, the researcher explained to the students the purpose of the study, what it aimed to discover and how respondents would benefit from it. Then the researcher clearly gave the instructions on how to answer the adopted reading tool. The PhilIRI post reading tool was photocopied respective to the number of identified grade 7 students. The respondents were given ample time to answer the questionnaire. After they answered the questionnaires silently, the researcher scheduled another day for the Oral reading.

The results of the reading comprehension test were then kept with utmost confidentiality and follow the privacy act section 16 the rights of the data subject and section 20 the security of personal information.

Post -Data Collection Phase. After the silent and oral reading examinations were conducted, the researcher collected the data from the respondents. The statistical tools were conceptualized for interpretation and analysis of the data gathered. Then all the utilized data were stored and kept in a safety place for security purposes and for future references

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher employed different statistical treatments in analysing the data to be gathered from the respondents. These statistical treatments were essential in analysing the data gathered from the tests that were given to the respondents. The statistical treatments utilized for the study were the Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Standard Deviation, Shapiro-Wilk Test, and Spearman-Rho.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This statistical analysis was used to determine the frequency and percentage distribution in assessing the reading proficiency level of the grade 7 learners in their oral and silent reading.

Median. This descriptive statistical analysis determines the average silent and oral reading proficiency of the students.

Standard deviation. This was used to measure the dispersion of the silent and oral reading scores relative to the median.

Shapiro-Wilk Test. This was used to determine the distribution of the silent and oral reading scores whether it was normally distributed or not.

Spearman-Rho. This was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between silent and oral reading proficiency and students' academic performance in English.

Ethical Considerations

Every individual possesses the entitlement to personal privacy and the safeguarding of their private information. To address this matter, the researcher dispatched a parental consent letter to the parents or guardians of the learners involved in the study. Given that a portion of these participants are minors, the letter explicitly stated that their involvement is entirely voluntary. Additionally, comprehensive guidance and orientation were administered to underage participants after parental consent and the affixing of signatures.

It is guaranteed that data confidentiality will be rigorously maintained. To adhere to the ethical standards of research and prevent any infringement upon the human rights of the participants and other relevant individuals contributing to the research's execution, the subsequent ethical precautions have been taken into account.

Risks and Benefits. This research employs a correlational design, utilizing the Phil-IRI tool to evaluate learners' oral and silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English. The study adhered to ethical guidelines, as the Institutional Review Board (IRB) cannot approve research that jeopardizes respondents' well-being, dignity, or privacy. In the case of this study, the researcher believed that it poses no significant or potential risks to the respondents. There was no intention to engage in data mining, and the research instrument (Phil-IRI tool) is designed to prevent any possibility of causing psychological distress to the participants. As a result, the study aimed to be beneficial for the respondents. The study's outcomes were intended to offer guidance to English teachers in implementing enhancement reading remediation programs.

Conflict of Interest. There are no conflicts of interest in terms of finance or other personal conflicts within the research study, the researcher, and the participants. Any conflict to arise amidst the study will be disclosed to all who are involved. The true and only purpose of the study was to assess the relationship between the reading proficiency level and academic performance in English among grade 7 students as basis for enhancement program. The research study did not have hidden agendas towards making the paper.

Vulnerability Assessment. The researcher found no possible harm that could affect minors among the collected data. All the gathered information was favorable and respected the dignity of individuals, including minors. The only remaining tasks were to obtain parental approval, to provide information and guidance, and to ensure the data's confidentiality and privacy. Data mining is unnecessary, as the evaluation will solely rely on provided criteria.

Respect for Persons

In this research study, respondents were voluntarily participating. The potential respondents were provided with informed consent to relay all the topics and investigations included in the study. Respondents had the right to decline the invitation for any reason they have. All respondents who accepted the invitation were treated with equal respect as with those who turned down the invitation. The researcher secured that the participation and the data to be gathered would be strictly confidential.

Justice

The researcher and the research study treated the involved respondents equally with fairness. It included the inclusion criteria that no discrimination will occur towards the capabilities of the respondents. If a particular factor such as mental incapacity is to be encountered

with a respondent, they will be informed duly on their exclusion for the study. All respondents were addressed with the same respect. The researcher ensured that the research study would consistently uphold the proper manner of treating subjects from selection to actual participation. The benefits included are solely for gratitude for participating in the research study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data which answers the questions in this research. The results are presented, analyzed, and discussed in this portion in the following sequence: reading proficiency level of learners both in oral and silent reading, and academic performance of learners in English among grade 7 students. Likewise, this chapter presents the relationship between oral and silent reading proficiency and learners' academic performance in English. Furthermore, the reading intervention program enhancement based on the results of the study is also presented in this chapter.

Learners' Reading Proficiency

The table below presents the reading proficiency level of grade 7 learners, both in oral and silent reading. Reading proficiency refers to the ability to read, comprehend, interact, and get connected with a piece of text. It also refers to the process of describing and assessing learners and the teaching of reading proficiency.

Oral Reading Proficiency Level of Grade 7 Learners

Oral reading ability is used to predict learners' overall reading ability. It is used to assess three aspects of reading: accuracy, rate, and fluency, all of which have been found to be highly related to understanding. Learners are asked to read aloud from grade-level passages. Listening to learners read aloud gives important insights into the hidden cognitive processes that are employed to analyze and comprehend written content.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Grade 7 Learners' Oral Reading Proficiency*

<i>Equivalent Comprehension Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
80%-100%	Independent	15	8.1%
59%-79%	Instructional	11	5.9%
58% Below	Frustration	160	86.0%
Total		186	100.0%

n = 186

The data illustrates the distribution of comprehension levels among grade 7 learners which shows that grade seven learners belong to Frustration level in their Oral Reading Proficiency. The majority of learners, constituting 86.0%, are experiencing frustration in their comprehension, scoring below 58%. This suggests a significant challenge in understanding the given material within this population. On the other hand, 5.9% fall within the instructional range (59%-79%), indicating a moderate level of understanding with room for improvement. A smaller portion, 8.1%, demonstrates independent comprehension, scoring between 80% and 100%, showcasing a higher level of self-sufficiency in understanding the content. This breakdown highlights the diverse range of comprehension levels within the group, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches to address the varying needs and challenges in comprehension as it highly agreed to Gardner (2019) the remedial program must be specific, realistic, and attainable.) This finding is consistent with the 2018 PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) results, which showed that the Philippines ranked last among 79 nations in terms of reading comprehension.

The table below presents the results of Oral Reading Proficiency of Grade 7 Learners using Shapiro-Wilk.

Table 2. *Oral Reading Proficiency OF Grade 7 Learners*

<i>N</i>	<i>HPS Median</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Level W</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>Description</i>
Oral Reading	186	40	16.5	5.00	Frustration
0.916	< .001				

The table shows the oral reading proficiency score and level of the grade 7 learners. It was revealed that the average oral proficiency score of the grade 7 learners was 16.5 (sd = 5.00) with a highest possible score of 40. Thus, the learners got an oral reading proficiency rate of 41.25% which was interpreted as readers under Frustration level. This implied that readers find reading materials so difficult that they cannot successfully respond to them (Flippo, 2014) It further meant that learners, in average, had the reading level with below 90% accuracy where decoding words, vocabulary and concepts are too difficult for them. It was also revealed in the table that the data on oral reading proficiency was not normally distributed ($W = 0.916$, $p < .001$).

The results which revealed that Grade 7 learners are, in average, categorized as Frustrated readers concurred with Pressley's (2017) findings where it was mentioned that the difficulties that second-language readers encounter are a result of their lack of vocabulary and linguistic knowledge. Furthermore, according to Joshi (2017), there is a significant relationship between fluency and grammar; hence, those who lack vocabulary have difficulty interpreting written material.

Learners' Silent Reading Proficiency

Silent reading fluency is a person's ability to read quietly with focus, at acceptable reading rates, and with clear understanding. This ability bridges the gap between word recognition and understanding (Price, et al, 2015).

The table below presents the Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Grade Seven Learners' Silent Reading Proficiency Level.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Grade Seven Learners' Silent Reading Proficiency Level*

<i>Equivalent Comprehension Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
80%-100%	Independent	10	5.4%
59%-79%	Instructional	14	7.5%
58% Below	Frustration	162	87.1%
	Total	186	100.0%

n = 186

The frequency and percentage distribution presented in the table provide valuable insights into the silent reading proficiency levels of Grade Seven learners. It was revealed that majority of Grade Seven learners fall within the frustration range which constituted 87.1% of the total population, indicating challenges in silent reading proficiency. This group faces difficulties in comprehending texts, suggesting a need for targeted interventions and support to enhance their reading skills. Identifying and addressing the specific areas of struggle within this cohort is crucial for fostering improvement.

The table below presents the results of Silent Reading Proficiency Level of Grade 7 Learners.

Table 4. *Silent Reading Proficiency Level of Grade 7 Learners*

	<i>N</i>	<i>HPS</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>Shapiro-Wilk</i>	
						<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>
Silent Reading	186	40	15.0	3.77	Frustration	0.921	< .001

The table shows the silent reading proficiency score and level of the grade 7 learners. It was revealed that the average silent reading proficiency score of the grade 7 learners was 15.0 (sd = 3.77) with a highest possible score of 40. Thus, the learners got silent reading proficiency rate of 37.5% which was interpreted as Frustration Level. This implied that readers find reading materials so difficult that they cannot successfully respond to them (Flippo, 2014) when they are asked to read a selection independently and answer comprehension questions in order to assess reading rate and reading comprehension level. It was also revealed in the table that the data on silent reading proficiency was not normally distributed ($W = 0.921$, $p < .001$).

This study challenges the findings of Samuels, Hiebert, and Rasinski (2016), suggesting that contrary to their results, silent reading rates might not surpass oral reading rates in the early stages of reading proficiency. Even for pupils in the 50th percentile in the elementary grades, data on oral and silent reading norms reveal that quiet reading rates are at least 30% higher than oral reading rates. In the current study, oral reading rates are higher than silent reading rates. According to Pretorius (2016), however, decoding skill does not necessarily result in a complete comprehension of what is written in the text. Some readers comprehend the material but fail to find meaning in it. Thus, based on comprehension, one may begin to distinguish between a good and a poor reader. A reader with high decoding abilities but low literacy development is fundamentally a poor reader since they are unable to make sense of what they have read.

Academic Performance in English

This section presents the academic performance in English of the learners. Academic performance in English is a measure of a learner's accomplishment in English. Teachers and education authorities often assess the achievement of learners through classroom performance tasks, written outputs, and quarterly test scores.

Academic Performance in English of the Grade 7 learners

The table below presents a comprehensive overview of the academic performance in English for Grade 7 learners. The data is summarized using key statistical measures, shedding light on the central tendencies and distribution of final grades.

Table 5. *Results of the Academic Performance in English of Grade 7 Learners*

	<i>N</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>Shapiro-Wilk</i>	
					<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>
Final Grade	186	79.0	4.35	Satisfactory	0.951	< .001

The table shows the academic performance of the grade 7 learners in English. It was revealed that the average academic performance of the grade 7 learners in English was 79.0 (sd = 4.35). The median final grade of 79.0 and the "Satisfactory" level indicate a moderate overall performance among Grade 7 learners in English. This meant that most of the grade 7 learners got Satisfactory grades in English. It was also revealed in the table that the data on academic performance in English was not normally distributed ($W = 0.951$, $p < .001$).

In conclusion, while the overall performance is satisfactory, the non-normal distribution prompts further investigation to better understand the nuances affecting Grade 7 learners' performance in English. This information can guide targeted interventions and instructional strategies to enhance academic outcomes.

Distribution of Academic performance of Grade 7 students Final Grade in English

The table below presents the results of the Distribution of Academic Performance of Grade 7 Students for the Final Grade in English.

Table 6. *Academic Performance of Grade 7 Students for the Final Grade in English*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90-100	Outstanding	16	8.6%
85-89	Very Satisfactory	20	10.8%
80-84	Satisfactory	120	64.5%
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	30	16.1%
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%
	Total	186	100%

n = 186

The academic performance of Grade 7 learners in the final grade is depicted in Table 6. Among the students, 16 of them, constituting 8.6% of the total, achieved an outstanding performance, securing grades between 90 and 100. Following closely, 20 learners, representing 10.8%, attained a very satisfactory level, with grades ranging from 85 to 89. A significant portion of the cohort, 120 students (64.5%), achieved a satisfactory performance, scoring between 80 and 84. Additionally, 30 learners (16.1%) fell into the category of fairly satisfactory, obtaining grades between 75 and 79. Impressively, none of the students scored below 75, indicating that all learners met the minimum expectations. Overall, out of the total 186 students, each individual's academic performance was captured, presenting a comprehensive overview of their achievements in the final grade. Research on the relationship between reading comprehension techniques and academic achievement was done by Hijazi (2019). The results show that reading comprehension techniques and academic achievement are positively correlated. The results also showed a connection between academic achievement and reading challenges.

From the table 2, the academic performance is measured by two (2) areas, namely: Written Work (40%) and Performance Task (60%) based on DepEd Order No. 031, s. 2020.

Relationship Between Oral and Silent Reading Proficiency and Learners' Academic Performance in English

This section presents the relationship between oral and silent reading proficiency and learners' academic performance in English.

Oral Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance in English

Table 7 presents the Spearman's rho result between the oral reading proficiency and academic performance in English of the Grade 7 learners.

Table 7. *Correlation Between Oral Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance in English*

		<i>Oral Reading</i>	<i>Final Grade</i>
Oral Reading Proficiency	Spearman's rho		
	p-value		
Academic Performance in English	Spearman's rho	0.407	
	p-value	<.001	

The table shows the correlation matrix on oral reading proficiency and academic performance in English of grade 7 learners. The Spearman's rho test of correlation revealed that oral reading proficiency had a weak positive correlation to the academic performance in English ($r = 0.407$). This implied that as the oral reading proficiency of the learners increases or decreases, their academic performance in English also increases or decreases, respectively. Moreover, the table revealed that oral reading proficiency was statistically correlated with academic performance in English ($p < .001$) at 0.05 level of significance. This suggested that there is a linear relationship between the two variables, the oral reading proficiency level and students' academic performance.

This result is consistent with the findings of Cadiz-Gabejan and Quirino's (2021) study, which suggests a direct proportional linear relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance, indicating that students with higher reading proficiency demonstrated higher academic performance than those with average reading performance. As a result, the study concluded that learners require an intervention program to improve their reading abilities and become independent readers. It should be emphasized, however, that the study described did not emphasize testing learners' oral reading skills, but rather their overall reading proficiency.

Similarly, in a study of lower primary school students in Ghana (Nyarko et al., 2018), proficiency in reading was found to be strongly and positively associated to children's success on all standard performance assessments.

Interestingly, this result contradicts the findings of Torio (2019), who researched the Oral Reading Proficiency Test (ORPT) Result and its Relationship to Grade Seven Students' Academic Performance in English. There was not a significant relationship formed in the results on the academic performance of the students when classified according to independent, instructional, and frustration level in both word recognition and comprehension. However, it was underlined that the learners' reading profiles were not positively stable in terms of word recognition and word comprehension since learners did not consistently do well when assessed in these areas.

Thus, this empirical data will be useful to both schools and educators in improving each learner's reading proficiency and their academic performance.

Silent Reading Proficiency And Academic Performance In English

Table 8 presents the Spearman's rho result between the silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English of the Grade 7 learners.

Table 8. *Correlation Between Silent Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance in English*

		Silent Reading	Final Grade
Silent Reading	Spearman's rho	—	
	p-value	—	
Academic Performance in English	Spearman's rho	0.139	
	p-value	0.058	

The table shows the correlation matrix on silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English of grade 7 learners. The Spearman's rho correlation test found a weakly positive link between silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English ($r = 0.139$). This meant that the learners' academic performance in English would likewise increase or decrease depending on how well they perform in silent reading. Moreover, the table revealed that silent reading proficiency was not statistically correlated with the students' academic performance in English ($p < .058$) at 0.05 level of significance. This suggested that the weak correlation between silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English occurred on the account of chance coincidence in the sample but was not present in the entire population.

The findings do not totally match with Hijazi's (2018) study on the relationship between students' reading comprehension and their achievement in English, which indicated a statistically significant relationship between students' reading comprehension and achievement in English because reading comprehension positively enhances students' achievement.

Limitations. While quantitative approaches provide exact measures and comparisons, they may not represent the full complexities of students' proficiency in reading. Although it gives valuable insights into the link between oral/silent reading proficiency and academic performance in English, it does not take into account the influence of other potentially influencing variables on learners' reading proficiency. A mixed-methods strategy that blends quantitative analysis with qualitative insights might help future study.

The study relies on the Phil-IRI to assess reading skills (both oral and silent reading) and the learners' grade to assess academic performance in English. Future research may employ alternative instruments to assess the aforementioned characteristics, particularly academic achievement, which includes a variety of aspects such as written work, varied performance activities, and a quarterly exam.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher would like to conclude that the results supported the Information Processing Model Theory which promotes oral reading fluency strategies for learners as well as the significance of factors outlined in the Reading Systems Framework for enhancing the reading proficiency and academic performance of grade seven learners in English at Tipolo National High School. In addition, with the integration of the Connectivism Learning Theory, language teachers can leverage digital tools and resources to create a networked learning environment for an enhanced reading remediation program. Incorporate online platforms, educational websites, and digital libraries to provide a variety of materials and reading sources. With the use of adaptive learning technologies, language teachers can adjust the difficulty and pace of reading activities based on individual progress. This helps tailor the enhanced remediation program to the specific needs and abilities of each learner.

The following are the recommendations according to the findings of the study.

Implement targeted reading techniques tailored to each learner's needs to boost their reading proficiency.

Offer additional instructional resources and diverse reading materials to support English learners in improving their academic performance.

Implement a targeted reading intervention program focusing on enhancing both oral and silent reading techniques. This program aims to elevate students' English proficiency from a Satisfactory level to a Very Satisfactory one, thereby boosting their overall academic performance.

Language teachers should incorporate specialized programs focusing on enhancing oral reading skills. This could involve incorporating

interactive reading sessions, pronunciation exercises, and fluency-building activities into the English curriculum.

Conduct targeted research in the field, actively testing diverse reading strategies and employing a range of evaluation tools. This hands-on approach aims to significantly boost learners' reading proficiency

Teachers should also find other implications of reading comprehension towards students' academic success.

Both teachers and parents must collaborate to promote family and community involvement in reading comprehension like organizing literacy programs focused on reading comprehension.

The Department of Education should create concrete policies and practices to address the perennial problem of developing the learner's reading comprehension and academic performance.

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